

Landscape features shape people's perception of ecosystem service supply areas.

Garau Enrica^{a,b*}, Pueyo-Ros Josep^{a,c}, Jiménez-Aceituno Amanda^d, Peterson Garry^d, Norström Albert^d, Ribas Palom Anna^a, Vila-Subirós Josep^a

^a *Department of Geography, Institute of Environment, IMA-UdG, University of Girona, 17071 Girona, Spain*

^b *Department of Biology and Geology, University of Almeria, La Cañada de San Urbano, 04120 Almeria, Spain*

^c *ICRA, Catalan Institute for Water Research, 17003 Girona, Spain*

^d *Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden*

**Corresponding author. E-mail address: egarau@ual.es*

Abstract

Landscapes have typically been produced by varied, diverse, and long-term interactions between people and nature. However, most landscape planning and ecosystem service mapping approaches focus on the biophysical aspects of landscapes rather than the social. Spatial representations of people's perceptions, mental models, and local knowledge of ecosystem services can be created using participatory mapping. This study uses participatory mapping to identify how people's perceptions of provisioning, regulating and cultural ecosystem service supply areas coincide or mismatch with the landscape features of two Mediterranean river basin areas in north-eastern Catalonia, Spain. We found that the random forest and geographically weighted regression techniques are able to strongly associate landscape features with stakeholders' perceptions of ecosystem service supply areas. These results demonstrate that the stakeholders associate various geographic elements with different types of ecosystem service supply areas. Visible geographical features, such as a reservoir, mountains, wetlands, showed great importance in the perception of supply areas of ecosystem services, compared to ecological or biophysical indicators, when mapping and spatially associating certain benefits to ecosystem service supply areas. These findings reveal that, often, the ecological processes and dynamics of functioning of ecosystems are invisible and not fully understood. We argue that integrating these aspects into participatory landscape planning, policies and practice can make the invisible visible and, consequently, increase the understanding for a more targeted and effective management. This could allow stakeholders to better understand the ecological processes behind the visible geographic features of the landscape, fostering a shared knowledge and better environmental management outcomes.

Keywords: Social-ecological systems, Water ecosystem services, Stakeholder perception, Participatory mapping, Spatial metrics, Spatial analysis

Acknowledgements. We thank all respondents of our study for their attention and time

Funding. This study was funded with the financial support of the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the project "Incentives and barriers to water conservation in the tourism sector. Analysis and proposals for efficient water management" (CSO2016-75740-P).

Conflicts of Interest. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data availability. The data used in this study is available in a Zenodo repository at <https://zenodo.org/record/7562080#.Y86zI3bMKUk>

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Social-ecological systems are characterized by multiple social and ecological interactions that reshape
3 both ecological and social structures (Berkes and Folke, 1998; Martín-López et al., 2017). These
4 systems often emerge through long-term dynamics of social-ecological co-evolution and co-
5 production (Folke et al., 2021). Landscapes, as social-ecological systems, exhibit patterns that result
6 from long-term ecological, biophysical, and geological processes, such as species dispersal, erosion,
7 and plate tectonics, as well as social-ecological dynamics shaped by activities like farming, irrigation,
8 and travel (Palomo et al., 2016).

9 Ecosystem services provide a conceptual framework to examine and analyze social-ecological
10 interactions (Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010). Ecosystems offer multiple services that support human
11 life and well-being. The production and access to these services arise from complex relationships
12 between people and nature. Interactions that generate ecosystem services can range from deliberate
13 design to emergent patterns (Bennett et al., 2009). For instance, ecosystem services can be derived
14 from highly engineered ecosystems like reservoirs and dams, as well as from the mosaic landscapes
15 that have evolved over centuries of settlement and urbanization.

16 Mapping ecosystem services is a technique increasingly used in environmental decision-making and
17 landscape management (Cowling et al., 2008; Palomo et al., 2013). This approach encompasses
18 various methods, including examining cascades of ecosystem services and analyzing the social-
19 ecological co-production of ecosystem services. It considers the biophysical, social, cultural, and
20 economic dimensions in the assessment of ecosystem services (Burkhard and Maes, 2017).

21 The ecosystem services approach often emphasizes biophysical values and metrics (Biggs et al., 2011;
22 Brown et al., 2012; Burgos-Ayala et al., 2020b). Models for ecosystem services typically rely on data
23 regarding distinct spatial features of the landscape, including elevation, geological characteristics,
24 and distribution maps of plants and animal species (Bryan et al., 2010; De Vreese et al., 2016b). These
25 models are used to estimate the spatial distribution of biological, land, and water resources, as well
26 as their interrelations (Bryan et al., 2010). Such ecologically focused knowledge has often influenced
27 conservation planning and setting management priorities for conservation and natural resource
28 management (Brown et al., 2012; Bryan et al., 2010b; Cowling et al., 2008; Raymond et al., 2009;
29 Burgos-Ayala et al 2020).

30 However, there is a need to develop and test approaches that integrate social and ecological factors
31 in the analysis and modeling of ecosystem services (Bryan et al., 2010; De Vreese et al., 2016a,
32 2016b). Since social-ecological systems emerge from interactions, it is expected that social and
33 ecological factors are interconnected. This raises important questions: What are the spatial
34 relationships between social values and landscape features? How do different geographical features
35 relate to people's perception of ecological processes and interactions? (Alessa et al., 2008; Brown and
36 Reed, 2012; De Vreese et al., 2016b, 2016a).

37 Social theories and data have not been extensively utilized in designing models and metrics for
38 conservation and natural resource management (Dressel et al., 2018; García-Nieto et al., 2015;
39 Martín-López et al., 2017; Rocha et al., 2020). However, social factors, including perceptions, power
40 relations, and mental models of landscape features, play a crucial role in shaping ecosystem service
41 patterns in a landscape (Meacham et al., 2016; Reyers et al., 2013). Furthermore, social factors
42 strongly influence the distribution and access to ecosystem services among different stakeholders, as
43 well as changes in landscape structures and patterns (De Vreese et al., 2016b; Felipe-Lucia et al.,
44 2015).

45 The perceptions of landscapes held by people are important because they can significantly influence
46 the way landscapes are reshaped and planned, thereby impacting the assessment and implementation
47 of landscape solutions (Biggs et al., 2011; Whitfield et al., 2011). Research that explores the
48 relationship between these perceptions and biophysical and geographical landscape features is needed
49 to enhance our understanding of landscape social-ecological dynamics and interactions (Brown and
50 Reed, 2012; Bryan et al., 2010; García-Llorente et al., 2015; Rocha et al., 2020).

51 Participatory mapping is a valuable method for creating spatial representations of people's
52 perceptions, mental models, and local knowledge of ecosystem services (Alessa et al., 2008; Brown
53 et al., 2012; Cowling et al., 2008; García-Nieto et al., 2015). It can also be used to explore people's
54 perceptions of ecosystem service supply areas (Castro et al., 2013; Fagerholm et al., 2016; García-
55 Nieto et al., 2015; Palomo et al., 2013). Participatory mapping links people's value systems with
56 ecosystem services, biophysical, and geographical features of a landscape in a spatially explicit
57 manner. By analyzing differences in stakeholders' perceptions, participatory mapping enables more
58 inclusive approaches to environmental management. Moreover, the collaborative process of
59 participatory mapping can foster collaboration, co-production, and the co-design of a shared vision
60 of the landscape among participants. These methods have the potential to increase stakeholder
61 awareness of the wide range of social-ecological dynamics and facilitate the development of more
62 effective environmental policies with social support (Cowling et al., 2008).

63
64 This study utilizes participatory mapping to examine the alignment or divergence between
65 stakeholders' perceptions and landscape features in two Mediterranean river basin areas in
66 northeastern Catalonia, Spain. River basins are the product of ongoing changes in social-ecological
67 interactions (European Commission, 2000; Martín-López et al., 2017). In river basins, understanding
68 ecological processes and their spatial distribution is crucial for managing aquatic ecosystems and
69 water ecosystem services, as people modify the landscape to ensure sustainable delivery of these
70 services to beneficiaries (Emmett et al., 2016).

71 The research builds upon a participatory mapping dataset developed in previous studies conducted in
72 the same study context (see Garau et al., 2021a, 2020). In Garau et al. (2020), the perceptions of local
73 stakeholders regarding ecosystem services were analyzed through interviews and a participatory
74 mapping exercise. This helped identify supply areas, beneficiaries, and vulnerable areas based on
75 stakeholder perceptions. In contrast, the study by Garau et al. (2021a) focused on analyzing the spatial
76 patterns of ecosystem service flows using participatory mapping data. The study explored spatial
77 relationships, such as distance, direction, and concentration of beneficiaries between supply and
78 demand areas, aiming to identify potential conflicts among local actors.

79 The central novelty of this study, in comparison to previously published results, lies in the comparison
80 of the participatory mapping database with multiple spatial metrics. This methodological approach,
81 not previously explored in existing research, seeks to identify coincidences or mismatches and
82 examine the interrelationships between participatory data and spatial metrics. The study aims to
83 critically reflect on the implications of integrating stakeholders' social understandings of ecological
84 processes into participatory and decision-making processes for conservation policies and landscape
85 planning.

86 Therefore, the objectives of this study are as follows:

87 i) Identify the interrelationships between perceptions and spatial metrics to explore possible spatial
88 coincidences and mismatches between them.

- 89 ii) Investigate how ecological variables and geographic features influence perceptions of water
90 ecosystem services supply areas.
91 iii) Discuss and reflect on the importance and added value of participatory ecosystem services
92 mapping in the implementation of environmental policies.
93

94 **2. Methods**

95 *2.1 Study area description*

96 This research was conducted in the Muga and Fluvià river basins, located in northeastern Catalonia,
97 Spain, just below the French border (Figure 1). These basins are characterized as Mediterranean river
98 basins and experience a Mediterranean climate, with mild and humid autumns-springs and hot and
99 dry summers, often accompanied by prolonged periods of drought. The sociocultural process of co-
100 evolution between ecosystems and human activities has resulted in the development of these
101 Mediterranean basins, which exhibit areas of extreme ecological and sociocultural diversity (Blondel,
102 2006). The Muga river basin covers a surface area of 854 km², with a river length of 64 km, while
103 the Fluvià river basin is slightly larger, covering a surface area of 974 km² and with a river length of
104 97 km.

105 Water flows in the Muga river are regulated for water production purposes, whereas the Fluvià river
106 maintains an ecological flow regime. The flow of the Muga river is controlled by the Darnius-
107 Boadella Reservoir, which serves as the primary water supply source for the entire basin. Along most
108 of the middle section of the river, the average annual flow of the Muga river is 2.5 m³/s (IDESCAT,
109 2020). The unregulated Fluvià river follows a Mediterranean flow pattern, characterized by high
110 water levels in autumn and spring, and low water levels in summer. The entire length of the Fluvià
111 river is protected by the Nature 2000 Network, with well-preserved riparian forests that serve as
112 important ecological corridors connecting different Natura 2000 sites, including the Muga river. The
113 ecological flow, which represents the minimum water flow required to sustain the river ecosystems,
114 varies significantly along the course of the Fluvià river, ranging from 1.5 m³/s upstream to 10 m³/s
115 downstream.

116 Both the Muga and Fluvià rivers originate in the East Pyrenees and flow into the Aiguamolls de
117 l'Empordà Natural Park, a protected landscape (Category V IUCN) that includes three strict nature
118 reserves (Category Ia IUCN). The area has been part of the Ramsar International Network of
119 Protected Wetlands since 1993 (Ramsar, 1999). The river basins exhibit a diversity of topographic,
120 climatic, and environmental features, as well as various land uses, activities, and water demands
121 (Pascual et al., 2016). Over the past six decades, severe droughts and water scarcity episodes have
122 become increasingly intense, particularly in the Muga River basin. During this period, water demand
123 in the basin has continuously risen. The Muga River basin has witnessed an increase in intensive crop
124 and livestock farming, as well as urban and tourism development, particularly along the coast. These
125 factors have contributed to tensions and conflicts over increasingly scarce water resources (Saurí et
126 al., 2000; Tàbara and Saurí, 2004). In contrast, in the Fluvià River basin area, local stakeholders
127 generally perceive water scarcity only during periods of intense drought. Both basins can be
128 understood as social-ecological systems, as the landscape has been shaped by dynamic interactions
129 between society and ecosystems. Additionally, water-related social-ecological infrastructure, such as
130 historic irrigation canals, mills, and water fountains, hold significant social and cultural
131 importance (Saurí et al., 2000).

Figure 1. Muga and Fluvià river basins are located in Northeastern Catalonia, Spain. Red lines show watershed boundaries. The rivers flow from the Pyrenees to the Mediterranean. In the mountains the river basins are adjacent. At the coast the wetlands of the Aiguamolls de l'Empordà Natural Park define a sub-watershed that is located between the two river basins.

132

133

2.2 Data Collection

134

135

136

137

138

139

140

141

142

2.2.1 Participatory mapping exercise

143

144

145

146

147

148

149

150

151

152

153

154

155

156

Our participatory mapping process followed the methods developed by Palomo et al. (2013). To determine the water ecosystem services to be mapped, we consulted a panel of six water management experts from different fields who were familiar with both river basins. These experts were asked to identify the most important water ecosystem services based on the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Goods and Services (CICES) (v5.1) (v5.1) (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018). From the list, the experts selected six services: two provisioning services (water for irrigation and drinking water), two regulating services (biodiversity and water regulation), and two cultural services, namely aesthetic values and opportunities for recreational activities (e.g., swimming, fishing, kayaking, bird watching) (Plato and Meskin, 2014).

To ensure a diverse representation of stakeholder groups, we used non-proportional quota sampling rather than aiming for a proportional sample of each group (Raymond et al., 2009; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). We expanded the initial list of potential participants with the help of stakeholders identified in previous studies conducted in the same area (Ricart Casadevall, 2014; Ventura Pujolar, 2005). For more details on stakeholder selection, refer to Garau et al. (2020). The stakeholder groups

157 comprised individuals from the administrative, agricultural, environmental protection, industrial, and
 158 tourism sectors. Out of 63 stakeholders contacted, 51 agreed to participate, with 27 from the Muga
 159 river basin and 24 from the Fluvià river basin (Table 1). The mapping interviews were conducted
 160 between June 2019 and July 2020.

161 During the mapping interviews, stakeholders were provided with a map of the basins and asked to
 162 place dots representing water ecosystem services. They had the freedom to place as many dots as they
 163 deemed necessary. Following the approach proposed by Brown et al. Brown et al. (2012) and
 164 Raymond et al. (2009), we utilized a paper mapping system as it offers accessibility, space for
 165 discussion, promotes participation, and facilitates the identification of spatial characteristics and
 166 distribution of water ecosystem services (Fagerholm et al., 2019; Plieninger et al., 2013; Pocewicz et
 167 al., 2012). For each water ecosystem service, stakeholders were instructed to map the corresponding
 168 ecosystem service supply areas, which are the locations where the service is produced (Palomo et al.,
 169 2013). They marked these areas on a 1:50,000 topographic map of the basins using colored dots with
 170 a radius of 1 cm, equivalent to a circle with a radius of 500 m. A pixel size of 500 m was utilized for
 171 generating heatmaps (see Figure 2) (García-Nieto et al., 2015; Palomo et al., 2013; Pérez-Ramírez et
 172 al., 2019). Vertical photographs were taken of each completed map, which were later converted into
 173 digital images for data analysis.

174
 175 **Table 1.** Stakeholders' characterization per stakeholder group and river basins.

Frequencies of Group	Watershed	
	Fluvià	Muga
Administrative - political level	2	3
Administrative - technical level	3	3
Crop – Livestock farmers (Agricultural)	3	4
Environmental groups and associations	2	2
Industrial-Hydroelectric	5	0
Natural Protected Areas	2	2
On site recreational tourism sector	4	4
Recreational leisure tourism sector	2	6
Tourism business sector	1	3

176
 177 *2.2.2 Spatial metrics*

178 In order to compare the data obtained from the participatory mapping exercise with spatial metrics,
 179 we calculated a set of spatial metrics that served as proxies for representing the biophysical,
 180 geographical, and ecological characteristics of the study area. The selection of these metrics aimed to
 181 capture a wide range of ecological aspects specific to the river basins, considering both regionally
 182 important factors and data availability constraints. Our goal was to choose metrics that would provide
 183 a comprehensive representation of planning, ecological, and biophysical attributes of the landscape.
 184 Due to limitations in data availability in the study area, we selected a total of 15 spatial metrics, which
 185 were categorized into three groups: i) Conservation geography metrics based on criteria from the
 186 Regional Plan for the study areas (1 metric); ii) Ecological geography metrics representing various

187 biophysical landscape characteristics (10 metrics); iii) Hydrological geography metrics (4 metrics)
 188 that pertained to the key ecosystems and geographical components crucial for the production and
 189 regulation of ecological interactions in water-related processes within the river basins.

190 To calculate these spatial metrics, we utilized data from diverse sources, including vegetation
 191 classification maps, animal distribution maps, species richness indices, biological productivity
 192 mapping, normalized vegetation indices (NDVI), and net primary productivity (NPP) indices (Alessa
 193 et al., 2008; Luck, 2007; Zhao et al., 2016).

194 Table 2 provides an overview of the selected spatial metrics, along with the sources and processes
 195 used for generating the corresponding maps. Each metric was calculated on a raster map with a
 196 resolution of 500 m, consistent with the resolution of the perception heatmaps, as explained in the
 197 following section (see 2.3.1 section).

198

199

Table 2. Characteristics of selected spatial metrics.

Group	Spatial metric	Description	Database
i) Conservation geography	Priority conservation status levels	The Regional Plan of the study area, which represents the urban and territorial planning tool used to establish conservation actions with legal values, establish 4 priorities conservation levels (ENPE level; Special protection level; Territorial protection level; Preventive protection level). We assigned a value of priority for each category, classifying the conservation status from 0 (no protection) to 5 (maximum protection), according to the Regional Plan.	Regional Plan
ii) Ecological geography	Areas with high forest value	Areas considered by the Regional Plan with a high forest value and importance	Regional Plan
	Areas with high agricultural value	Areas considered by the Regional Plan with a high agricultural value and importance	Regional Plan
	Nesting Suitability	It is computed as the suitability of each landscape parcel for pollinator nesting are based on expert opinion and published literature.	Aries (Artificial Intelligence for ecosystem services) Database (Villa et al., 2014)
	Flowering Suitability	It describes the occurrence of flowers suitable to serve as food for pollinator insects are based on expert opinion and published literature. Land cover types are used to the probability of such flowering occurring in each point.	Aries Database
	NPP (Kg/ha)	Net Primary Productivity (NPP), or the production of plant biomass, is equal to all of the carbon taken up by the vegetation through photosynthesis (called Gross Primary Production or GPP) minus the carbon that is lost to respiration. $NPP = GPP - \text{respiration}$.	Aries Database
	Leaf Area Index	Describes the proportion of area covered by leaved found above a given area of soil.	Aries Database
Forest fragmentation	Time-series forest fragmentation data have been developed by Naimi, based on global European Space Agency-Climate Change Initiative (ESA-CCI) land cover data. Naimi defines the 'forest' class by aggregating all 14 trees cover related land cover types from the ESA CCI product into one class. We further define eight non-forest classes (agriculture, grassland, wetland, settlement, sparse vegetation, bare area, water, permanent snow and ice) that we use as multinomial categorical data, or as binary categorical data (to define forest vs. non-forest). These	Aries Database	

classes follow the reclassification used by Mousivand & Arsanjani.
(Values from 0 to 1)

NDVI	The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is an indicator of the greenness of the biomes (300 m resolution). Even though it is not a physical property of the vegetation cover, its simple formulation makes it widely used for ecosystems monitoring. (Values from -1 to 1). More technical information about the NDVI 300 m, such as temporal coverage, projection, resolution etc., can be found at: https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/NDVI	Copernicus Global Land Services
Species Richness	It represents the species distribution based on UTM grids. For this, the Inventory consists of a 10 × 10 km UTM grid mapping and a database with the taxonomic information of the species and the UTM grid codes by which they are distributed. The key taxonomic groups in the inventory are birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, invertebrates, fish, vascular flora, and non-vascular flora. Values represent the distribution of biodiversity through the maximum levels of the number of species per grid and delimiting by taxonomic group the grids in which ranges of numbers of species are distributed.	Spanish government Database (Inventario Español de Especies Terrestres (IEET))
DEM Elevation (m)	25 x 25 m resolution Digital Elevation Model. It is a digital representation of the surface of the terrain by means of the regular or irregular sampling of the altitude of the relief, usually of the planet Earth (see: https://www.icgc.cat/en/Citizens/Learn/Dictionaries/Model-digital-d-elevacions)	Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya)
iii) Hydrological geography	Reservoir Rivers Aquifers Wetlands	Each of these metrics indicates the presence or absence of the geographical features of aquatic ecosystems – water features.
		Catalan Water Agency (Agència Catalana d'Aigua) Database

200
201

2.3 Data Analysis

2.3.1 Creation of a combined participatory and spatial metrics database

202 The results obtained from the participatory mapping exercise were digitized and analyzed using QGIS
203 v.3.10 (QGIS Development Team, 2020). Vector layers were created by converting the points on the
204 maps into digital format, including information such as water ecosystem services category, name, and
205 stakeholder profile. A total of 7,146 points, representing the paper dots from the mapping exercise,
206 were digitized and divided into 18 layers to represent the mapped water ecosystem services and their
207 distribution across the two river basins.

208 To estimate the point density, we calculated kernel density rasters in QGIS using the Kernel function
209 (qgis:heatmapkerneldensityestimation). A mobile window (radius) of 5,000 m was used, which
210 provided a continuous surface, and the cell resolution (pixel size) was set to 500 m, matching the size
211 of the map dots (Baumeister et al., 2020; Palomo et al., 2013). The resulting heatmaps for each water
212 ecosystem service were combined and overlaid to identify hotspots representing the supply areas for
213 specific services (e.g., drinking water, irrigation water, biodiversity) as well as for each water
214 ecosystem services category (provisioning, regulating, and cultural).
215

216 To calculate the spatial metrics, we georectified all spatial maps, ensuring that they had the same
217 extent, resolution, and reference system. Subsequently, the maps were scaled from 0 to 1 to create a
218 datacube for spatial metrics using the stars package v.0.2. (Pebesma, 2021) for R 4.1. (R Core Team,
219 2020). This data standardization allowed for the intercomparison among the different maps.

220 2.3.2 Statistical Analysis

221 The statistical analysis consisted of two stages: i) testing the predictive power of spatial metrics for
222 perceived ecosystem services density, and ii) characterizing the spatial relationships between spatial
223 metrics and mapped ecosystem services.

224 To assess the predictive capability of spatial metrics for water ecosystem services perceived by
225 stakeholders, we employed Random Forest Regression (Breiman, 2001). The data were split into
226 three categories: provisioning, regulating, and cultural. A random forest consisting of 300 trees was
227 trained on each category. The training data comprised 80% of the observations, while the remaining
228 20% were used for validation, following the standard practice in machine learning studies. The model
229 was tuned by varying parameters such as the size of predictors' sample (3, 6, 9, 12, and 15), minimal
230 node size (3, 5, 7, 9), and proportion of bootstrap samples (0.55, 0.632, 0.70, and 0.80). Prediction
231 error was assessed using unseen observations from models with the smallest "leave-one-out cross-
232 validation" error in the training phase (one model for each category of ecosystem services) (Hastie et
233 al., 2021).

234 To characterize the spatial relationships between spatial metrics and mapped ecosystem services and
235 analyze their spatial distribution within the study area, we employed Geographically Weighted
236 Regression (GWR) (Akaike, 1974). A sample of 6000 points was used, and a GWR bandwidth of 0.1
237 was selected after evaluating multiple attempts with different values. We constructed a model using
238 the variables that exhibited greater importance in the Random Forest model. Subsequently, a stepwise
239 selection was performed using local R^2 as the selection criterion to arrive at the final model, where
240 water ecosystem services perception served as the dependent variable and all spatial metrics were
241 considered as explanatory variables. Three separate models were fitted, one for each category of
242 ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, and cultural).

243 The advantage of combining the random forest and GWR methods is twofold: firstly, the random
244 forest captures non-linear relationships that are relevant across the entire study area, and secondly,
245 the GWR model reveals these global relationships by providing spatially varying coefficients for each
246 variable and the direction of these relationships. Each value in the GWR model represents a local
247 coefficient for a specific point, using 600 points in its vicinity for regression analysis. Thus, after
248 identifying the variables with the strongest relationships, GWR enables the examination of these
249 relationships in a spatial context, illustrating their behavior at each point within the river basin.

250 The random forest model analysis was conducted using the ranger package (Wright and Ziegler,
251 2017), while the Geographically Weighted Regression model employed the spgwr package v.0.6-34
252 (Bivand and Nakaya, 2013). All analyses were performed in R 4.1. (R Core Team, 2020).

253

254 3. Results

255

256 3.1 Descriptive Analysis results

257 The descriptive analysis revealed a relatively balanced distribution of perceived water ecosystem
258 services between respondents from the Muga and Fluvia River basins, indicating no significant
259 differences in the spatial distribution of services identified by stakeholders. Consequently, we present
260 the results for both river basins combined. Among the identified services, regulating service supply
261 areas (biodiversity and water regulation) received the highest number of points, totaling 2,873 (41%).
262 This was followed by cultural service supply areas (aesthetic values and recreational activities) with
263 2,917 points (40%), and provisioning service supply areas (drinking and irrigation water) with 1,359

264 points (19%). For a more detailed breakdown of the number of points mapped by stakeholders for
 265 each specific water ecosystem service, refer to Garau et al. (2021, 2020). Figure 2 provides a visual
 266 representation of how stakeholders mapped the distribution of provisioning, regulating, and cultural
 267 ecosystem service supply areas.
 268

Figure 2. Maps show smoothed spatial perception of ecosystem service provision areas across the river basins based on digitalized participatory maps. Numbers indicate different concentration of mapped ecosystem services. Darker colours mean higher concentration of mapped water ecosystem services by stakeholders, while lighter colour mean a lower concentration. The different heatmaps were combined and overlaid to obtain ecosystem service hotspots, smoothed across the points, using a mobile window (radius) of 5000 m (chosen as the optimal size after several trials) and a cell resolution (pixel size) of 500 m (the same size as the colored mapping dots). The process is explained in detail in in Garau et al. (2020).

269
 270 Stakeholders identified a diverse range of perceived ecosystem service supply areas. In terms of
 271 provisioning water ecosystem services, areas such as the Darnius-Boadella reservoir, wells, irrigation
 272 canals, and dams along the river were identified. For regulating and cultural water ecosystem services,
 273 stakeholders pointed out forestland in the upper basin, mountains, rivers, and wetlands as significant
 274 supply areas. Cultural water ecosystem service supply areas also included water-related heritage
 275 elements like mills, fountains, and factories, as well as cycling and hiking paths, the river mouth, and
 276 the wetlands. Notably, wetlands were particularly recognized as important supply areas for regulating
 277 and cultural water ecosystem services.

278
 279 *3.2 The contribution of distinct ecological factors, conservation status, and geographic features for*
 280 *predicting perceived water ecosystem services supply areas*

281 The Random Forest Model successfully predicted the density and spatial distribution of water
 282 ecosystem services with a small error of +0.02 / -0.02 (values ranging from 0 to 1). The R^2 values
 283 ranged from 0.85 to 0.92, depending on the category of water ecosystem services (Figure 3). This
 284 demonstrates a strong association between spatial metrics and the perceived supply areas of water
 285 ecosystem services in the landscape.

286 Regarding provisioning water ecosystem services, the most influential variables were the presence of
 287 aquifers, species richness, reservoirs, leaf area index, and elevation (Figure 3). Similarly, aquifers,
 288 wetlands, species richness, and elevation were among the top predictors for regulating and cultural
 289 water ecosystem services. Wetlands, in particular, were not a significant predictor for provisioning
 290 services but exhibited a strong influence on cultural and regulating water ecosystem services.
 291

Figure 3. Variable importance plots of the random forest models according to ecosystem services categories. The x axis refers to the weight each variable has in predicting the density and spatial position of perceived ecosystem services, while the y axis refers to the variables included in the model. Lighter bars refer to anthropogenic features. The dashed lines indicated where variables' influence is greater than 5% (expected influence by chance).

292 *3.3 The interrelations of factors on the local spatial distribution of perceived water ecosystem*
 293 *services supply*

294 The results of the geographically weighted regression model reveal that the spatial relationships
 295 between spatial metrics and mapped water ecosystem services are not evenly distributed across the
 296 study area (Figure 4). The local R^2 values, calculated at each sample point, vary significantly
 297 throughout the region, indicating differences in the predictive power of spatial metrics for the three
 298 categories of ecosystem services.

299 High R^2 values can indicate either a positive or negative correlation. In other words, they can represent
 300 a direct positive relationship between specific environmental variables and the presence of ecosystem
 301 services as perceived by stakeholders, or a negative relationship between environmental variables and
 302 the spatial distribution of identified ecosystem services.

303 For cultural and provisioning water ecosystem services, higher R^2 values were generally observed in
 304 the eastern, upper, and southern parts of the two river basins. This aligns with the Cap de Creus natural
 305 park, which is considered an important area for the local community, as well as significant forested
 306 areas in the upper regions and the protected wetlands located at the river mouths. These areas are
 307 known for their social and cultural significance to the local community. On the other hand, for
 308 regulating services, higher R^2 values were found in the western and southern parts of the basins,
 309 coinciding with important forested areas in the upper regions and the protected wetlands and river
 310 mouths in the lower regions.

311 Lower R^2 values were observed in the western and central parts of the basins for cultural and
 312 provisioning services, and in the central and eastern parts for regulating services. These findings
 313 indicate variations in the spatial distribution of ecosystem services within the study area.

314
 315
 316

Figure 4. Local R^2 results of the GWR model calculated for the three different categories of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, and cultural). Higher values mean more significant relationships between the 15 spatial metrics and the density of perceived water ecosystem services, while lower values show less significant relationships. The lines in black represent the river basin areas of the Fluvià (the one on the left side) and of the Muga (the one on the right side).

317

318 Similarly, the global coefficients of the variables also exhibited positive and negative values
 319 depending on different parts of the study area and specific categories of ecosystem services (Figure
 320 5). Higher positive or negative values indicate stronger relationships between the 15 spatial metrics
 321 and the density of perceived water ecosystem services, while values closer to zero suggest less
 322 significant relationships.

Figure 5. Summary of GWR coefficient estimated at each sample point for the 15 variables selected as spatial metrics for each category of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, and cultural). The variables are grouped by anthropocentric and natural features plus the intercept of the models calculated at each point; and ordered by median value within each group. The different colours represent the three categories of ecosystem services.

323

324 Therefore, positive coefficients indicate that as those variables increase, the density of perceived
 325 water ecosystem services also increases. In contrast, negative coefficients indicate that an increase in
 326 those variables corresponds to a decrease in the density of perceived water ecosystem services.

327 On a general scale, we found that variables such as rivers and protection levels were not particularly
 328 significant, with coefficients ranging between -1 and 1. Additionally, variables including species
 329 richness, agricultural and forest values, elevation, and NDVI index were not significant, with
 330 coefficients near 0.

331 In more detail, for cultural ecosystem services, the variables reservoir and wetlands exhibited higher
 332 positive coefficients, while nesting suitability, leaf area index, forest fragmentation, and NPP

333 variables showed negative coefficients, indicating a decrease in the density of perceived water
 334 ecosystem services associated with the presence of those variables. For provisioning services, higher
 335 positive values were especially associated with reservoirs and aquifers, while higher negative
 336 coefficients were not particularly significant and were associated with NPP, forest fragmentation, and
 337 nesting suitability. Finally, concerning regulating services, the variables reservoir, wetlands, and
 338 aquifers had higher positive coefficients. Forest fragmentation, nesting suitability, and leaf area index
 339 showed negative coefficients, although they were not significant (values near 0).

340 The GWR coefficients revealed the importance of each variable in relation to a specific spatial point
 341 and the three different categories of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, and cultural),
 342 highlighting local-scale differences that were not captured in a global interpretation of the model
 343 (Figure 6). The results demonstrated variations across the three categories of ecosystem services.
 344

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of the coefficients of each variable used in the geographically weighted regression model, according to the three categories of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, and cultural). The lines in black represent the river basin areas of the Fluvià (the one on the left side) and of the Muga (the one on the right side).

345
 346 For instance, the aquifers variable exhibited higher values (between 30 and 40) in the central and
 347 southern parts of the river basins for provisioning and regulating services. These areas corresponded
 348 spatially to the aquifers and river mouths, which were identified as important water supply areas by
 349 local stakeholders within the river basins. Similarly, the NPP variable showed higher values (close to
 350 20) primarily in the lower parts of the two river basins for all three categories of ecosystem services.
 351 These areas coincided with the protected wetlands, the main Muga and Fluvià rivers, and the forested
 352 regions.

353 Furthermore, the species richness variable displayed higher values in the lower parts of the river
 354 basins, particularly for cultural ecosystem services, aligning with the protected wetlands. However,
 355 it was not strongly associated with the forested areas in the upper part of the river basins. In the Fluvià
 356 river basin, species richness exhibited high values for regulating ecosystem services, predominantly
 357 related to the tributaries and main rivers of Muga and Fluvià.

358 The spatial distribution of all coefficients can be found in Appendix A.

359

360 4. Discussion

361 Firstly, we present stakeholders' perceptions of water ecosystem services. Secondly, we discuss
 362 mismatches in the river basin landscape, specifically focusing on the presence or absence of spatial

363 associations with spatial metrics. Lastly, we reflect on the direct implications that integrating social
364 data has for environmental policies and adaptive landscape management.

365

366 *4.1 Stakeholders' perceptions of water ecosystem services*

367 Our observations revealed the following key findings: i) Stakeholders associated ecosystem services
368 with distinct spatial supply areas, with each category of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating,
369 and cultural) being related to different landscape features. Wetlands, aquifers, forests, and rivers were
370 strongly associated with all types of water ecosystem services, albeit with variations based on their
371 categories. For instance, reservoirs were particularly linked to provisioning services, while wetlands
372 and aquifers were strongly associated with regulating services. Wetlands also showed a strong
373 association with cultural services; ii) Stakeholders associated both natural and artificial features
374 depending on the categories of ecosystem services. Identified features ranged from natural elements
375 such as forests, aquifers, and wetlands, to constructed features such as wells, distribution channels,
376 and reservoirs.

377 The random forest model successfully predicted the density of water ecosystem services, highlighting
378 that stakeholders associated a specific set of geographic elements based on the categories of
379 ecosystem services. Aquifers and species richness (a proxy for biodiversity) were identified as
380 important predictors for all categories of ecosystem services. The presence or absence of mountains
381 (elevation) and vegetation cover (leaf area index) were slightly less important predictors for all
382 categories. Wetlands were associated with cultural and regulating services, while reservoirs were
383 associated with provisioning services.

384 This demonstrates that stakeholders spatially associated different categories of ecosystem services
385 with distinct geographical and biophysical features. This association was particularly evident for
386 provisioning services, such as drinking and irrigation water, which were predicted with higher
387 accuracy based on biophysical elements like reservoirs and groundwater wells. Regulating and
388 cultural water ecosystem services, on the other hand, were predicted with greater accuracy using
389 wetlands, mountains (or their absence), species richness, and the protection levels of the landscape.

390 Our findings highlight that stakeholder perceptions of ecosystem services are based on their
391 interpretation of specific landscape elements (Palomo et al., 2016). This suggests that stakeholders
392 consider certain ecosystem services to be socially and ecologically co-produced (Andersson et al.,
393 2015a, 2015b; Palomo et al., 2016; Raudsepp-Hearne and Peterson, 2016), involving both natural and
394 anthropogenic landscape features. Focusing solely on one type of ecosystem service in an assessment
395 of these river basins would not have revealed the importance of different landscape features.
396 Therefore, our results emphasize the significance of considering diverse value systems and
397 knowledge in shaping human perceptions of a place (IPBES, 2022; Peterson et al., 2018).
398 Incorporating different value systems into management practices benefits from a spatial approach and
399 acknowledges the context-specific perspectives of stakeholders (Gottwald et al., 2021), which expose
400 the importance of diverse and multiple understandings of biophysical, geographical, and ecological
401 factors (Dressel et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2018). This approach also highlights the attention paid
402 to different landscape features at both individual and collective levels (Biggs et al., 2011; Garau et
403 al., 2021b).

404

405 *4.2 Stakeholders' perception and misperception about landscape*

406 While our findings consistently linked stakeholders' perceptions of ecosystem services to certain
407 landscape features, they also revealed significant gaps in perceiving the important parts of the
408 landscape that contribute to ecosystem services. This highlights the presence of common
409 "misperceptions" or mismatches in understanding the less visible and dynamic processes of
410 ecosystems, such as the role of forest areas in aquifer recharge and soil retention (Pascual et al., 2016).
411 Our study revealed that stakeholders perceived the entire upper part of the river basin as unimportant
412 for the provision of water ecosystem services because it was not visibly connected to aquatic features
413 and visible water flows. Consequently, people tend to associate provisioning areas with visible
414 aquatic elements like reservoirs or rivers, rather than recognizing the implicit role of forest areas in
415 water storage and the water cycle.

416 For instance, stakeholders frequently identified wells and water distribution channels as supply areas
417 but seldom recognized other critical landscape characteristics such as forest areas, which hydrologists
418 know are essential for maintaining water availability in wells (Zabalza-Martínez et al., 2018). These
419 divergent and subjective understandings of ecological processes highlight the disconnection between
420 certain geographic and ecological elements as perceived by society, hindering a holistic
421 understanding of ecological processes.

422 Nevertheless, our findings also demonstrated a reasonable level of spatial association between the
423 mapped water ecosystem services and spatial metrics. This association was stronger than in some
424 previous studies (De Vreese et al., 2016b; Schneiders et al., 2012; Whitehead et al., 2014), which
425 found limited spatial coincidence between spatial metrics and people's perceptions of nature. Similar
426 spatial mismatches, as observed in our study, have been attributed to three factors in previous research
427 (Brown and Fagerholm, 2015; De Vreese et al., 2016b): i) spatial metrics encompass the entire study
428 area while participatory data focuses on water ecosystem services; ii) the scientific definition of
429 ecological variables does not align with stakeholders' conceptualization of those variables; iii) people
430 generally exhibit less interest in the biophysical elements of the landscape compared to socio-cultural
431 aspects, resulting in fewer identifications of those elements. Each of these factors could contribute to
432 the spatial mismatches between stakeholders' perceived landscape characteristics and the spatial
433 metrics representing those characteristics.

434 However, both the random forest and geographically weighted regression models accurately
435 identified high levels of spatial coincidence between ecological data and participatory data. The
436 geographically weighted regression model revealed that the perception of landscape features varies
437 across the river basins and the selected categories of ecosystem services (see Figure 5). For example,
438 a significant contribution of the species richness variable was observed in predicting biodiversity
439 services (Schneiders et al., 2012) in the Natural Park of the Aiguamolls. However, stakeholders did
440 not associate species richness with biodiversity in the forest areas of the upper basin.

441 This finding underlines the subjective nature of stakeholders' perceptions of the landscape (Gottwald
442 et al., 2021). It appears that certain spatial metrics often associated with the production of ecosystem
443 services are not considered by stakeholders when associating the spatial distribution of ecosystem
444 service supply areas in the river basins. We also observed a negative relationship between variables
445 related to agricultural and forest values and perceived supply areas (see Appendix A). Although
446 statistically significant to a minimal extent, geographically weighted regression highlights that as
447 agriculture increases in the agricultural plain situated in the lower, eastern portion of the basin, the
448 importance of predicting the concentration of water ecosystem services decreases. This finding aligns
449 with the perception that upstream parts of the river basin serve as areas for maintaining ecological

450 processes and integrity, while downstream areas are primarily perceived as areas of ecosystem service
451 demand (García-Llorente et al., 2015). This pattern can also be explained by the perception that
452 agricultural areas promote provisioning services such as food, leading to spatial trade-offs with other
453 services like water quality regulation or biodiversity (Butler et al., 2013). Geographically weighted
454 regression also highlighted a similar behavior for the forest value. The upper part of the basin, despite
455 its scientifically recognized ecological importance in generating ecosystem services (González-
456 García et al., 2021; Pascual et al., 2016), was associated with a lower density of perceived ecosystem
457 service supply areas, particularly in relation to biodiversity.

458 459 *4.3 Social models and perceptions of landscape matter in environmental policies and adaptive* 460 *landscape management*

461 The understanding of which areas provide ecosystem services (Martín-López et al., 2012) and the
462 spatial assessment of social values are crucial for landscape policies (Gottwald et al., 2021). Our
463 results indicate that people tend to view the landscape in a fragmented rather than integrated manner
464 (Rothman, 2012), with important implications. It suggests that environmental and management
465 policies based solely on popular perception may not align with the actual functioning of river basins
466 (Gobster et al., 2007). Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the extent of these mismatches and
467 work towards addressing them to enhance stewardship, management, and planning for the future of
468 these river basins (Jones et al., 2013; Lokocz et al., 2011). These aspects are particularly relevant in
469 our case study, where water availability is decreasing over time, exacerbated by rising temperatures,
470 prolonged drought periods, and increased social conflicts over water use (Garau et al., 2022).

471 For instance, understanding the necessity of implementing forest management policies in the upper
472 part of the basin to ensure water availability in the lower part is crucial for sustainable water resource
473 use, ecosystem protection, and the maintenance of "invisible" services like water recharge, erosion
474 control, and hydrological regulation (Bennett et al., 2009; Green et al., 2015). Failure to recognize
475 the interconnectedness of the river basin as a whole and viewing it as separate and isolated parts
476 hinders the comprehension of why forest management in the upper basin is vital for sustainable water
477 resource use in the lower basin (Sodhi et al., 2010). Developing shared perceptions of landscape
478 functioning based on common knowledge of social-ecological processes is essential for effective river
479 basin management. Our results underscore the importance of stakeholders' values influencing their
480 understanding and knowledge of landscape processes, and vice versa (García-Llorente et al., 2015).
481 Comparing local perceptions with spatial metrics reveals two key findings: i) stakeholders possess
482 expert knowledge of their local landscape, and ii) understanding their landscape perceptions and the
483 factors that shape them is crucial (Brown et al., 2004).

484 Therefore, understanding how people perceive landscapes is a critical issue for social acceptance of
485 environmental policies. Stakeholders' perceptions of the landscape are influenced by socially defined
486 landscape classifications (Rothman, 2012; Svobodová, 1990). Our findings indicate that people
487 consider the conservation status to be important for ecosystem service production, with protected
488 wetlands being perceived as more crucial ecosystem service supply areas than forest areas.

489 This finding highlights two significant aspects to consider in landscape planning and environmental
490 policies. Firstly, it is important to understand why stakeholders tend to undervalue certain
491 ecologically relevant areas. Secondly, managing unprotected areas that stakeholders view as critical
492 for ecosystem services in a way that sustains their quality becomes crucial.

493 Participatory mapping data is a valuable tool for revealing stakeholders' views, understanding, and
494 interpretation of the landscape. It has the potential to identify "ecosystem services-based management
495 areas" and suggest specific policies to maintain the flow of these services (Palomo et al., 2013; Alessa
496 et al., 2008). Our findings demonstrate that stakeholders perceive the entire upper part of the river
497 basin as unimportant for water ecosystem services because it is not visibly connected to aquatic
498 elements (see Figure 5, Forest value metric). However, this area consists of forested regions that are
499 essential for water storage and regulation within the river basin.

500 This perceptual mismatch highlights the importance of environmental education, both in general
501 and as part of participatory planning processes. Essential ecological processes occur invisibly across
502 different spaces and times, often distant from people's daily perceptions. Therefore, environmental
503 education that reveals hidden processes and unveils ecosystem functions is crucial for fully
504 understanding ecological processes and their interactions with social and economic aspects (Menzel
505 and Bögeholz, 2009).

506 A social-ecological approach that emphasizes that landscape is not merely what we see, but also
507 depends on the invisible interrelationships between distinct ecosystems, ecological processes, history,
508 and infrastructure is essential for comprehending social-ecological landscapes (Brown and Reed,
509 2012).

510 The observed results underscore the need for critical reflection on the relationship between
511 participatory data and spatial metrics and the interconnection between these approaches. Such
512 reflection is crucial for integrating the diverse stakeholder landscape visions into participatory and
513 decision-making processes. Additionally, presenting these perceptions back to stakeholders during
514 participatory approaches can help foster a better understanding of the often-invisible ecological
515 processes behind the visible geographic features of the landscape and promote collaborative
516 behaviors and shared local ownership (Biggs et al., 2011; Brown and Fagerholm, 2015).

517 These important findings have direct implications for environmental policies and landscape planning.
518 For example, the invisibility of river basins and the non-perception of biodiversity loss should be
519 considered in conservation communication and the design of environmental policies. Concepts like
520 biodiversity loss are central to landscape management and conservation policies, and local
521 stakeholders' decisions can significantly influence landscape management and biodiversity
522 conservation (Kelemen et al., 2014). Thus, stakeholders' subjective understanding of ecological
523 concepts, such as biodiversity, hydrological flow, and water recharge, and their interpretation should
524 be integrated and taken into account when designing environmental policies and implementing
525 legitimate, accepted, and place-based solutions (Busse et al., 2021).

526

527 *4.4 Advantages, Limitations, and Methodological Lessons Learned*

528 In this section, we critically reflect on the advantages and limitations of our study, summarizing the
529 methodological lessons we have learned and their implications for interpreting the results.

530 One major novelty highlighted by our methodological approach, which combines random forest and
531 GWR methods, is the testing of whether spatial metrics can serve as good predictors of perceived
532 ecosystem services density identified through participatory mapping. Additionally, the approach
533 characterizes the spatial relationships between these metrics and perceived ecosystem services. Our
534 methodological approach revealed two key findings: firstly, the random forest analysis demonstrated
535 a strong association between spatial metrics and perceived water ecosystem services supply areas in
536 the landscape, identifying the contributions of ecological factors, conservation status, and geographic

537 features in predicting the density and spatial distribution of perceived ecosystem services. Secondly,
538 by selecting the most relevant spatial metrics for explaining the density of perceived ecosystem
539 services, the GWR model allowed us to explore the spatial relationships between these metrics at a
540 local level within the river basins.

541 This approach enabled us to uncover that spatial metrics and perceived water ecosystem services were
542 not evenly distributed throughout the study area, emphasizing specific points within the river basins
543 where these relationships were more or less significant.

544 However, we are also aware of the limitations of this methodological approach. Firstly, our study
545 does not include metrics explicitly related to ecosystem services due to the lack of available data in
546 the study area. The assessment primarily relies on proxies associated with the potential capacity to
547 provide respective ecosystem services. As a result, we cannot directly compare the ecosystem services
548 mapped by stakeholders with their supply areas. Without such a reference, the correlation between
549 perceptions of ecosystem services supply areas and contextual spatial metrics may be limited in
550 explanatory power. Including ecosystem services metrics in the overall analysis would be a valuable
551 step forward in identifying inconsistencies and misperceptions, as it would better associate
552 information on actual ecosystem services flow. This inclusion would support the understanding of
553 how participatory mapping approaches can contribute to improving society's comprehension of
554 ecological processes.

555 Secondly, the participatory mapping dataset focused on water ecosystem services, while the spatial
556 metrics used in this study encompassed a broader spectrum of landscape attributes beyond
557 hydrological aspects. This difference in focus may have influenced the interpretation of the final
558 results.

559

560 **5. Conclusion**

561 In this paper, we conducted a comparative analysis between spatial metrics and participatory mapping
562 data focused on water ecosystem services in a river basin area. Our objective was to examine spatial
563 coincidences and mismatches between these two datasets. We aimed to determine whether
564 biophysical characteristics and landscape elements were associated with stakeholders' perceptions of
565 water ecosystem services supply areas. Our findings underscored the significance of visible
566 geographical features, such as reservoirs, vegetation, mountains, and wetlands, in shaping the
567 perception of ecosystem service supply areas, as opposed to typically imperceptible ecological or
568 biophysical indicators. This integrative approach highlighted the importance of combining
569 stakeholders' perspectives with the local spatial characteristics of the landscape.

570 This study demonstrates the substantial potential of integrating spatial metrics and participatory data
571 for enhancing ecological outcomes and fostering a shared understanding of landscape functions and
572 processes (Alba-Patiño et al., 2021; Castro et al., 2011). By enhancing stakeholders' understanding
573 of ecological processes, their comprehension of the landscape will be deepened, thereby
574 strengthening their collective capacity to develop and implement strategies for addressing challenges
575 and fostering environmental stewardship (Gottwald et al., 2021). Integrating diverse perceptions and
576 understandings of the landscape in the co-construction and co-design of environmental policies and
577 objectives will result in greater social acceptance and improved ecological outcomes. Shared
578 understandings of the landscape facilitate the refinement of participatory targets in landscape
579 management and conservation policies and enhance stakeholders' awareness, adaptability, and
580 capacity to respond and adapt to social-ecological changes.

References

- Akaike, H., 1974. A New Look at the Statistical Model Identification. *IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr.* 19, 716–723. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1974.1100705>
- Alba-Patiño, D., Carabassa, V., Castro, H., Gutiérrez-Briceño, I., García-Llorente, M., Giagnocavo, C., Gómez-Tenorio, M., Cabello, J., Aznar-Sánchez, J.A., Castro, A.J., 2021. Social indicators of ecosystem restoration for enhancing human wellbeing. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105782>
- Alessa, L. (Naia), Kliskey, A. (Anaru), Brown, G., 2008. Social-ecological hotspots mapping: A spatial approach for identifying coupled social-ecological space. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 85, 27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2007.09.007>
- Andersson, E., McPhearson, T., Kremer, P., Gomez-Baggethun, E., Haase, D., Tuvendal, M., Wurster, D., 2015a. Scale and context dependence of ecosystem service providing units. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 12, 157–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.08.001>
- Andersson, E., Tengö, M., McPhearson, T., Kremer, P., 2015b. Cultural ecosystem services as a gateway for improving urban sustainability. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 12, 165–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.08.002>
- Baumeister, C.F., Gerstenberg, T., Plieninger, T., Schraml, U., 2020. Exploring cultural ecosystem service hotspots: Linking multiple urban forest features with public participation mapping data. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 48, 126561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126561>
- Bennett, E.M., Peterson, G.D., Gordon, L.J., 2009. Understanding relationships among multiple ecosystem services. *Ecol. Lett.* 12, 1394–1404. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01387.x>
- Berkes, F., Folke, C., 1998. Linking social and ecological systems: management practices and social mechanisms for building resilience, Cambridge. ed. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- Biggs, D., Abel, N., Knight, A.T., Leitch, A., Langston, A., Ban, N.C., 2011. The implementation crisis in conservation planning: Could “mental models” help? *Conserv. Lett.* 4, 169–183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00170.x>
- Bivand, Y., Nakaya, T., 2013. spgwr: Geographically weighted regression, R package version 0.6-34.
- Blondel, J., 2006. The “design” of Mediterranean landscapes: A millennial story of humans and ecological systems during the historic period. *Hum. Ecol.* 34, 713–729. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-006-9030-4>
- Breiman, L., 2001. Random Forests. *Mach. Learn.* 45, 5–32. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62008-0_35
- Brown, G., Fagerholm, N., 2015. Empirical PPGIS/PGIS mapping of ecosystem services: A review and evaluation. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 13, 119–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.10.007>
- Brown, G., Montag, J.M., Lyon, K., 2012. Public Participation GIS: A Method for Identifying Ecosystem Services. *Soc. Nat. Resour.* 25, 633–651. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2011.621511>
- Brown, G., Smith, C., Alessa, L., Kliskey, A., 2004. A comparison of perceptions of biological value with scientific assessment of biological importance. *Appl. Geogr.* 24, 161–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2004.03.006>
- Brown, G.G., Reed, P., 2012. Social Landscape Metrics: Measures for Understanding Place Values from Public Participation Geographic Information Systems (PPGIS). *Landsc. Res.* 37, 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01426397.2011.591487>
- Bryan, B.A., Raymond, C.M., Crossman, N.D., Macdonald, D.H., 2010. Targeting the management of ecosystem services based on social values: Where, what, and how? *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 97, 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2010.05.002>
- Burgos-Ayala, A., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Rozas-Vásquez, D., 2020a. Integrating Ecosystem Services in Nature Conservation for Colombia. *Environ. Manage.* 66, 149–161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-020-01301-9>
- Burgos-Ayala, A., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Torres-Torres, A.M., Rozas-Vásquez, D., Lam, D.P.M., 2020b. Indigenous and local knowledge in environmental management for human-nature connectedness: a leverage points perspective. *Ecosyst. People* 16, 290–303. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2020.1817152>
- Burkhard, B., Maes, J., 2017. Mapping Ecosystem Services. Pensoft Publishers, Sofia. <https://doi.org/10.5901/ichss-2012-vol-07>
- Busse, M., Zoll, F., Siebert, R., Bartels, A., Bokelmann, A., Scharschmidt, P., 2021. How farmers think about insects: perceptions of biodiversity, biodiversity loss and attitudes towards insect-friendly farming practices. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 30, 3045–3066. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02235-2>
- Butler, J.R.A., Wong, G.Y., Metcalfe, D.J., Honzák, M., Pert, P.L., Rao, N., van Grieken, M.E., Lawson, T.,

- Bruce, C., Kroon, F.J., Brodie, J.E., 2013. An analysis of trade-offs between multiple ecosystem services and stakeholders linked to land use and water quality management in the Great Barrier Reef, Australia. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 180, 176–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.08.017>
- Castro, A.J., García-Llorente, M., Martín-López, B., Palomo, I., Iniesta-Arandia, I., 2013. Multidimensional approaches in ecosystem services assessment. *Earth Obs. Ecosyst. Serv.* 441–468. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b15628>
- Castro, A.J., Martín-López, B., García-Llorente, M., Aguilera, P.A., López, E., Cabello, J., 2011. Social preferences regarding the delivery of ecosystem services in a semiarid Mediterranean region. *J. Arid Environ.* 75, 1201–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2011.05.013>
- Cowling, R.M., Egoh, B., Knight, A.T., O'Farrell, P.J., Reyers, B., Rouget, M., Roux, D.J., Welz, A., Wilhelm-Rechman, A., 2008. An operational model for mainstreaming ecosystem services for implementation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 105, 9483–9488. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0706559105>
- De Vreese, R., Leys, M., Dendoncker, N., Van Herzele, A., Fontaine, C.M., 2016a. Images of nature as a boundary object in social and integrated ecosystem services assessments. Reflections from a Belgian case study. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 22, 269–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.06.008>
- De Vreese, R., Leys, M., Fontaine, C.M., Dendoncker, N., 2016b. Social mapping of perceived ecosystem services supply-The role of social landscape metrics and social hotspots for integrated ecosystem services assessment, landscape planning and management. *Ecol. Indic.* 66, 517–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.01.048>
- Dressel, S., Ericsson, G., Sandström, C., 2018. Mapping social-ecological systems to understand the challenges underlying wildlife management. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 84, 105–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.03.007>
- Emmett, B.A., Cooper, D., Smart, S., Jackson, B., Thomas, A., Cosby, B., Evans, C., Glanville, H., McDonald, J.E., Malham, S.K., Marshall, M., Jarvis, S., Rajko-Nenow, P., Webb, G.P., Ward, S., Rowe, E., Jones, L., Vanbergen, A.J., Keith, A., Carter, H., Pereira, M.G., Hughes, S., Lebron, I., Wade, A., Jones, D.L., 2016. Spatial patterns and environmental constraints on ecosystem services at a catchment scale. *Sci. Total Environ.* 572, 1586–1600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.04.004>
- European Commission, 2000. Directive 2000/60/EU: European Water Framework Directive. *Off. J. Eur. Communities* 372(1).
- Fagerholm, N., Eilola, S., Kisanga, D., Arki, V., Käyhkö, N., 2019. Place-based landscape services and potential of participatory spatial planning in multifunctional rural landscapes in Southern highlands, Tanzania. *Landsc. Ecol.* 34, 1769–1787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-019-00847-2>
- Fagerholm, N., Oteros-Rozas, E., Raymond, C.M., Torralba, M., Moreno, G., Plieninger, T., 2016. Assessing linkages between ecosystem services, land-use and well-being in an agroforestry landscape using public participation GIS. *Appl. Geogr.* 74, 30–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2016.06.007>
- Felipe-Lucia, M.R., Martín-López, B., Lavorel, S., Berraquero-Díaz, L., Escalera-Reyes, J., Comín, F.A., 2015. Ecosystem services flows: Why stakeholders' power relationships matter. *PLoS One* 10, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0132232>
- Folke, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Galaz, V., Westley, F., Lamont, M., Scheffer, M., Österblom, H., Carpenter, S.R., Chapin, F.S., Seto, K.C., Weber, E.U., Crona, B.I., Daily, G.C., Dasgupta, P., Gaffney, O., Gordon, L.J., Hoff, H., Levin, S.A., Lubchenco, J., Steffen, W., Walker, B.H., 2021. Our future in the Anthropocene biosphere, *Ambio*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01544-8>
- Garau, E., Pueyo-Ros, J., Ribas, A., Vila-Subiros, J., 2021a. Follow the flow: Analysis of relationships between water ecosystem service supply units and beneficiaries. *Appl. Geogr.* 133, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2021.102491>
- Garau, E., Pueyo-Ros, J., Vila-Subiros, J., Ribas Palom, R., 2022. Deconstructing Ecosystem Service Conflicts through the Prisms of Political Ecology and Game Theory in a North - Western Mediterranean River Basin Conflicts through the Prisms of Political. *Hum. Ecol.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-022-00325-5>
- Garau, E., Torralba, M., Pueyo-Ros, J., 2021b. What is a river basin? Assessing and understanding the sociocultural mental constructs of landscapes from different stakeholders across a river basin. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 214, 104192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104192>
- Garau, E., Vila-Subiros, J., Pueyo-Ros, J., Ribas, A., 2020. Where do ecosystem services come from? Assessing and mapping stakeholder perceptions on water ecosystem services in the Muga river basin (catalonia, spain). *Land* 9, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9100385>
- García-Llorente, M., Iniesta-Arandia, I., Willaarts, B.A., Harrison, P.A., Berry, P., del Mar Bayo, M., Castro,

- A.J., Montes, C., Martín-López, B., 2015. Biophysical and sociocultural factors underlying spatial trade-offs of ecosystem services in semiarid watersheds. *Ecol. Soc.* 20. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07785-200339>
- García-Nieto, A.P., Quintas-Soriano, C., García-Llorente, M., Palomo, I., Montes, C., Martín-López, B., 2015. Collaborative mapping of ecosystem services: The role of stakeholders' profiles. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 13, 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.11.006>
- Gobster, P.H., Nassauer, J.I., Daniel, T.C., Fry, G., 2007. The shared landscape: What does aesthetics have to do with ecology? *Landsc. Ecol.* 22, 959–972. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-007-9110-x>
- González-García, A., Palomo, I., González, J.A., García-Díez, V., García-Llorente, M., Montes, C., 2021. Biodiversity and ecosystem services mapping: Can it reconcile urban and protected area planning? *Sci. Total Environ.* 803, 150048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150048>
- Gottwald, S., Albert, C., Fagerholm, N., 2021. Combining sense of place theory with the ecosystem services concept: empirical insights and reflections from a participatory mapping study. *Landsc. Ecol.* 0123456789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01362-z>
- Green, P.A., Vörösmarty, C.J., Harrison, I., Farrell, T., Sáenz, L., Fekete, B.M., 2015. Freshwater ecosystem services supporting humans: Pivoting from water crisis to water solutions. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 34, 108–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.06.007>
- Haines-Young, R., Potschin, M., 2018. Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V5.1 and Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure. [WWW Document]. URL www.cices.eu
- Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., James, G., Witten, D., 2021. An introduction to statistical learning (2nd ed.). Springer texts 102, 618.
- IDESCAT, 2020. Sistemas fluviales. Aportación. Por temporadas. Metodología [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.idescat.cat/pub/?id=aec&n=211&lang=es> (accessed 1.20.21).
- IPBES, 2022. Summary for policymakers of the methodological assessment regarding the diverse conceptualization of multiple values of nature and its benefits, including biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services (assessment of the diverse values and valuation of, International Institute for Sustainable Development).
- Jones, K.B., Zurlini, G., Kienast, F., Petrosillo, I., Edwards, T., Wade, T.G., Li, B. lian, Zaccarelli, N., 2013. Informing landscape planning and design for sustaining ecosystem services from existing spatial patterns and knowledge. *Landsc. Ecol.* 28, 1175–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-012-9794-4>
- Kelemen, E., García-Llorente, M., Pataki, G., Martín-López, B., Gómez-Baggethun, E., 2014. Non-monetary techniques for the valuation of ecosystem services, in: *OpenNESS Reference Book*. pp. 1–4.
- Lokocz, E., Ryan, R.L., Sadler, A.J., 2011. Motivations for land protection and stewardship: Exploring place attachment and rural landscape character in Massachusetts. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 99, 65–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2010.08.015>
- Luck, G.W., 2007. The relationships between net primary productivity, human population density and species conservation. *J. Biogeogr.* 34, 201–212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2006.01575.x>
- Martín-López, B., Palacios-Agundez, I., Montes, C., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Iniesta-Arandia, I., Palomo, I., Oteros-Rozas, E., Willaarts, B., Casado-Arzuaga, I., Amo, D.G. Del, Santos-Martín, F., González, J.A., Onaindia, M., García-Llorente, M., López-Santiago, C., 2012. Uncovering Ecosystem Service Bundles through Social Preferences. *PLoS One* 7, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0038970>
- Martín-López, B., Palomo, I., García-Llorente, M., Iniesta-Arandia, I., Castro, A.J., García Del Amo, D., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Montes, C., 2017. Delineating boundaries of social-ecological systems for landscape planning: A comprehensive spatial approach. *Land use policy* 66, 90–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.04.040>
- Meacham, M., Queiroz, C., Norström, A. V., Peterson, G.D., 2016. Social-ecological drivers of multiple ecosystem services: What variables explain patterns of ecosystem services across the Norrström drainage basin? *Ecol. Soc.* 21. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08077-210114>
- Menzel, S., Bögeholz, S., 2009. The loss of biodiversity as a challenge for sustainable development: How do pupils in Chile and Germany perceive resource dilemmas? *Res. Sci. Educ.* 39, 429–447. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-008-9087-8>
- Palomo, I., Felipe-Lucia, M.R., Bennett, E.M., Martín-López, B., Pascual, U., 2016. Disentangling the Pathways and Effects of Ecosystem Service Co-Production. *Adv. Ecol. Res.* 54, 245–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2015.09.003>
- Palomo, I., Martín-López, B., Potschin, M., Haines-Young, R., Montes, C., 2013. National Parks, buffer zones and surrounding lands: Mapping ecosystem service flows. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 4, 104–116.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.09.001>

- Pascual, D., Zabalza-Martínez, J., Funes, I., Vicente-Serrano, S.M., Pla, E., Aranda, X., Savé, R., Biel, C., 2016. Impacts of Climate and Global Change on the Environmental, Hydrological and Agricultura Systems in the LIFE MEDACC Case Study Basins. [WWW Document]. URL <http://medacc-life.eu> (accessed 6.24.20).
- Pebesma, E., 2021. stars: Spatiotemporal Arrays, Raster and Vector Data Cubes.
- Pérez-Ramírez, I., García-Llorente, M., Benito, A., Castro, A.J., 2019. Exploring sense of place across cultivated lands through public participatory mapping. *Landsc. Ecol.* 9, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-019-00816-9>
- Peterson, G.D., Harmáčková, Z. V., Meacham, M., Queiroz, C., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Kuiper, J.J., Malmborg, K., Sitas, N., Bennett, E.M., 2018. Welcoming different perspectives in IPBES: “nature’s contributions to people” and “ecosystem services.” *Ecol. Soc.* 23. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10134-230139>
- Plato, L., Meskin, A., 2014. Aesthetic Value. *Encycl. Qual. Life Well-Being Res.* https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_3349
- Plieninger, T., Dijks, S., Oteros-Rozas, E., Bieling, C., 2013. Assessing, mapping, and quantifying cultural ecosystem services at community level. *Land use policy* 33, 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.12.013>
- Pocewicz, A., Nielsen-Pincus, M., Brown, G., Schnitzer, R., 2012. An Evaluation of Internet Versus Paper-based Methods for Public Participation Geographic Information Systems (PPGIS). *Trans. GIS* 16, 39–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9671.2011.01287.x>
- QGIS Development Team, 2020. QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. Available at: <http://qgis.osgeo.org>.
- R Core Team, 2020. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing.
- Raudsepp-Hearne, C., Peterson, G.D., 2016. Scale and ecosystem services: How do observation, management, and analysis shift with scale—lessons from Québec. *Ecol. Soc.* 21. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08605-210316>
- Raudsepp-Hearne, C., Peterson, G.D., Bennett, E.M., 2010. Ecosystem service bundles for analyzing tradeoffs in diverse landscapes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 107, 5242–5247. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0907284107>
- Raymond, C.M., Bryan, B.A., MacDonald, D.H., Cast, A., Strathearn, S., Grandgirard, A., Kalivas, T., 2009. Mapping community values for natural capital and ecosystem services. *Ecol. Econ.* 68, 1301–1315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2008.12.006>
- Reyers, B., Biggs, R., Cumming, G.S., Elmqvist, T., Hejnowicz, A.P., Polasky, S., 2013. Getting the measure of ecosystem services: A social-ecological approach. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 11, 268–273. <https://doi.org/10.1890/120144>
- Rocha, J., Malmborg, K., Gordon, L., Brauman, K., Declerck, F., 2020. Mapping social-ecological systems archetypes.
- Rothman, A., 2012. The Idea of Landscape. *Places J.* 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.22269/120801>
- Saurí, D., Ventura Pujolar, M., Ribas, A., 2000. Gestión del agua y conflictividad social en la cuenca del río Muga (Alt Empordá). *Geographicalia* 38, 59–76. https://doi.org/10.26754/ojs_geoph/geoph.2000381379
- Schneiders, A., Van Daele, T., Van Landuyt, W., Van Reeth, W., 2012. Biodiversity and ecosystem services: Complementary approaches for ecosystem management? *Ecol. Indic.* 21, 123–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.06.021>
- Sodhi, N.S., Lee, T.M., Sekercioglu, C.H., Webb, E.L., Prawiradilaga, D.M., Lohman, D.J., Pierce, N.E., Diesmos, A.C., Rao, M., Ehrlich, P.R., 2010. Local people value environmental services provided by forested parks. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 19, 1175–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-009-9745-9>
- Svobodová, H., 1990. Cultural Aspects of Landscape.
- Tàbara, D., Saurí, D., 2004. Stakeholders report on: The Muga River Basin Catalonia, Spain.
- Tashakkori, A., Teddlie, C., 2003. *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social & Behavioral Research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Villa, F., Bagstad, K.J., Voigt, B., Johnson, G.W., Portela, R., Honzák, M., Batker, D., 2014. A methodology for adaptable and robust ecosystem services assessment. *PLoS One* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091001>
- Whitehead, A.L., Kujala, H., Ives, C.D., Gordon, A., Lentini, P.E., Wintle, B.A., Nicholson, E., Raymond, C.M., 2014. Integrating biological and social values when prioritizing places for biodiversity conservation. *Conserv. Biol.* 28, 992–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12257>

- Whitfield, S., Geist, H.J., Ioris, A.A.R., 2011. Deliberative assessment in complex socioecological systems: Recommendations for environmental assessment in drylands. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 183, 465–483. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-011-1933-x>
- Wright, M.N., Ziegler, A., 2017. ranger: A Fast Implementation of Random Forests for High Dimensional Data in {C++} and {R}. *J. Stat. Softw.* 77, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v077.i01>
- Zabalza-Martínez, J., Vicente-Serrano, S.M., López-Moreno, J.I., Calvo, G.B., Savé, R., Pascual, D., Pla, E., Morán-Tejeda, E., Domínguez-Castro, F., Tague, C.L., 2018. The influence of climate and land-cover scenarios on dam management strategies in a highwater pressure catchment in Northeast Spain. *Water* 10, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10111668>
- Zhao, Q., Bai, J., Huang, L., Gu, B., Lu, Q., Gao, Z., 2016. A review of methodologies and success indicators for coastal wetland restoration. *Ecol. Indic.* 60, 442–452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.07.003>